

**IMPORTANCE OF METHODS OF WORKING WITH VISUALLY IMPAIRED
CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION *INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY,
MANAGEMENT AND COMMUNICATION***

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Abstract: Preschool education is one of the most important stages in children's lives. During this period, children form their personality, social skills and educational foundations. Working with visually impaired children in preschool education requires special attention. They have specific needs and difficulties, so special methods and approaches should be used in the educational process.

Key words: preschool education, visually impaired children, methods, educational institutions, individual approach, children, social skills, modern approach.

Visually impaired children have difficulties in fully understanding their surroundings due to their limited vision. The conditions and educational methods created for them in pre-school educational institutions have a great influence on their development. This is important for children's self-awareness, self-confidence and active participation in the social environment. When working with visually impaired children, first of all, it is necessary to determine their individual needs. Each child has its own characteristics, so it is important to use an individual approach in the educational process. This approach makes it possible to determine the specific development paths of children, taking into account their abilities and difficulties. There are many methods of working with visually impaired children in preschool education. Among them, the use of visual materials, games and interactive activities, as well as activities aimed at sensory development are important. Visual materials help children develop visual skills. Through colors, shapes and other visual materials, children better understand the environment. Games and interactive activities play an important role in developing the social skills of visually impaired children. Through games, children develop the skills to communicate with each other, express their thoughts and work in a team. This process helps them develop self-awareness and self-confidence. Activities aimed at sensory development help develop the senses of visually impaired children. Through

these activities, children get to know different materials, sounds and smells. Sensory development helps children increase their awareness of their environment and is important in strengthening their vision. Professional training of teachers is also important when working with visually impaired children in preschool education. Teachers should know special methods and approaches in working with visually impaired children. Their knowledge and skills help children successfully participate in the educational process. By understanding the needs of children and teaching them accordingly, teachers contribute greatly to their development.

Also, cooperation with parents is important in the process of preschool education. Parents play an important role in the development of their children and need to understand their needs. Regular communication with parents helps children successfully participate in the educational process. Parents should work together with teachers in developing their children's abilities. When working with visually impaired children, the social environment is also important. The social environment created in preschool educational institutions helps children to feel comfortable. A social environment allows children to communicate with each other, express themselves and develop social skills.

Cooperation between parents and teachers plays an important role in the development of children. This partnership helps children successfully participate in the educational process, develop social skills, and develop self-awareness. Regular exchange of information between parents and teachers helps to monitor changes in children's development. Parents can provide information about how their children are studying and behaving at home, and teachers need to inform parents about their activities and progress at school. Parents and teachers should set common goals for children's development. These goals should help children successfully participate in the educational process and should be aimed at developing their abilities. It is important that parents and teachers support each other. Parents should follow the teachers' recommendations and support their children's learning process. Teachers need to show parents how they can help their children's development. Parents and teachers work together to create a social environment that helps children feel comfortable. This

environment allows children to interact with each other and develop their social skills. Teachers should provide parents with the knowledge and skills necessary for their children's development. It is important for parents to know how they can help their child's education. Parents and teachers participating together in school activities help children develop social skills. These activities also serve to strengthen the relationship between parents and teachers. Parents and teachers need to understand the individual needs of children. This is important in the development of children, because each child has its own characteristics. Open and sincere communication between parents and teachers has a positive effect on children's development. Sharing ideas helps both parties learn more about the children.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, methods of working with visually impaired children in preschool education are very important. These methods support the development of children, taking into account their individual needs. Teachers, parents and the social environment help children to participate successfully in the educational process. When working with visually impaired children, the use of special methods and approaches helps to improve their quality of life and active participation in the social environment. By creating favorable conditions for visually impaired children, preschools can contribute to their future success.

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